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ADAPTIVE VOCABULARY CONSTRUCTION FOR FRUSTRATION INTENSITY MODELLING IN CUSTOMER SUPPORT DIALOG TEXTS

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ABSTRACT

This paper examines emotion intensity prediction in dialogs between clients and customer support representatives occurring on Twitter. We focus on a single emotion type, namely, frustration, modelling the user's level of frustration while attempting to predict frustration intensity on the current and next turn, based on the text of turns coming from both dialog participants. A subset of the Kaggle Customer Support on Twitter dataset was used as the modelling data, annotated with per-turn frustration intensity ratings. We propose to represent dialog turns by binary encoded bags of automatically selected keywords to be subsequently used in a machine learning classifier. To assess the classification quality, we examined two different levels of accuracy imprecision tolerance. Our model achieved a level of accuracy significantly higher than a statistical baseline for prediction of frustration intensity for a current turn. However, we did not find the additional information from customer support turns to help predict frustration intensity of the next turn, and the reason for that is possibly the stability of user's frustration level over the course of the conversation, in other words, the inability of support's response to exert much influence to user's initial frustration level.

KEYWORDS

Neural Networks, Emotion Annotation, Emotion Recognition, Emotion Intensity, Frustration

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A NEW APPROACH FOR RANKING SHADOWED FUZZY NUMBERS AND ITS APPLICATION

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ABSTRACT

In many decision situations, decision-makers face a kind of complex problems. In these decision-making problems, different types of fuzzy numbers are defined and, have multiple types of membership functions. So, we need a standard form to formulate uncertain numbers in the problem. Shadowed fuzzy numbers are considered granule numbers which approximate different types and different forms of fuzzy numbers. In this paper, a new ranking approach for shadowed fuzzy numbers is developed using value, ambiguity and fuzziness for shadowed fuzzy numbers. The new ranking method has been compared with other existing approaches through numerical examples. Also, the new method is applied to a hybrid multi-attribute decision making problem in which the evaluations of alternatives are expressed with different types of uncertain numbers. The comparative study for the results of different examples illustrates the reliability of the new method.

KEYWORDS

Fuzzy numbers, Intuitionistic fuzzy numbers, Shadowed sets, Shadowed fuzzy numbers, Ranking, Fuzziness measure.

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SIMULATION OF PACKAGE DELIVERY OPTIMIZATION USING A COMBINATION OF CARRIERS AND DROP- SHIP

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ABSTRACT

A variety of goods and services in the contemporary world requires evolutionary improvement of services e-commerce platform performance and optimization of costs. Contemporary society is deeply integrated with delivery services, purchasing of goods and services online, that makes competition between service and good providers a key selection factor for end-user.. As long as logistic, timely, and cost-effective delivery plays important part authors decided to analyse possible ways of improvements in the current field, especially for regions distantly located from popular distribution canthers and drop-ship delivery networks. Considering both: fast and lazy delivery the factor of costs is playing an important role for each end-user. The work proposes a simulation that analyses the current cost of delivery for e-commerce orders in the context of delivery by the Supplier Fleet, World-Wide delivery service fleet, and possible vendor drop-ship and checks of the alternative ways can be used to minimize the costs. Special attention is given to Drop-Ship networks as the factor of possible costs decrease. The main object of investigation is focused around mid and small companies living far from big distribution canthers, in the rural areas but actively using e-commerce solutions for their daily activities. The authors analysed and proposed a solution for the problem of cost optimization for packages delivery for long-distance deliveries using a combination of paths delivered by supplier fleets, worldwide, local carriers and drop-ship networks. Data models and Add-ons of contemporary Enterprise Resource Planning systems have been used, and additional development is proposed in the perspective of the flow selection change for combination of carriers. The experiment is based on data sources of the United States companies using a wide range of carriers for delivery services and uses the data sources of the real companies; however, it applies repetitive simulations to analyse variances in obtained solutions for different combinations of carriers.

KEYWORDS

Simulation, Customer Behavior, Drop-Ship, Optimization, E-commerce.

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DETERMINING BUSINESS INTELLIGENCE USAGE SUCCESS

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ABSTRACT

Business intelligence systems are highly complex systems that senior executives use to process vast amounts of information when making decisions. Business intelligence systems are rarely used to their full potential due to a poor understanding of the factors that contribute to system success. Organizations using business intelligence systems frequently find that it is not easy to evaluate the effectiveness of these systems, and researchers have noted that there is limited scholarly and practical understanding of how quality factors affect information use within these systems. This quantitative post positivist research used the information system (IS) success model to analyze how information quality and system quality influence information use in business intelligence systems. This study was also designed to investigate the moderating effects of maturity constructs (i.e., data sources and analytical capabilities) on the relationships between quality factors and information use.

KEYWORDS

Business Intelligence, information quality, system quality, systems maturity

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